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Pseudociste pankreasa- rezultati naše klinike*Pseudocysts of pancreas-results of our Clinic**M. Tatić, R. Jokić, S. Skeledžija-Mišković, G. Rakić .**Clinic of Pediatric Surgery, Institute for Child and Youth Health Care of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia*

Uvod: Abdominalna trauma u dečjem uzrastu je česta, a povrede pankreasa prate odsustvo simptoma ili razvoj akutnog abdomena. **Cilj:** Analiza učestalosti i terapijskog tretmana pseudocisti pankreasa. **Metode:** Obuhvaćeni su pacijenti hospitalizovani u petogodišnjem periodu (2005-2009). Na prijemu pored anamneze i pregleda, rađena je laboratorijska dijagnostika, ultrasonografija i CT dijagnostika, a potom su pacijenti smeštani u Jedinicu intenzivne terapije. Terapijski tretman je podrazumevao obustavljanje peroralnog unosa, parenteralnu nadoknadu tečnosti i elektrolita, plasiranje nazogastrične sonde uz aktivnu sukciju, antibiotike, analgeziju, blokatore H₂ receptora i/ili protonske pumpe, a ponekad i primenu Somatostatina. Lečenje je potom nastavljano konzervativnim ili operativnim metodama. **Rezultati:** Hospitalizovano je 7 pacijenata (3 muškog i 4 ženskog pola), uzrasta 3-13 godina (srednja vrednost 7,7 god). Mehanizam nastanka: 4 - povrede na upravljač bicikla, 1- udarac metalnom šipkom, 1- nakon primene antiepileptika (Eftil), a jedan pacijent je imao urođenu anomaliju (pancreas divisum). Vrednosti amilaza bile su višestruko povišene kod svih pacijenata. TPN trajala je prosečno 26 dana (3-42), kod 3 pacijenta primenjen je enteralni unos preko nazo-jejunalne sonde. Prosečna dužina hospitalizacije 61 dan (14-146). Terapija Somatostatinom primenjena je kod 3 pacijenta. Konzervativno su lečena 2 pacijenta, kod 2 je načinjena operativna eksterna drenaža, a kod 3 pacijenta interna (Roux-Y- cistoenterostomija). Letalan ishod zabeležen kod 1 pacijenta. **Zaključak:** Pseudociste pankreasa su retke u dečjem uzrastu i najčešće su posledica traume. Lečenje je kompleksno i dugotrajno, a ishod neizvestan.

Background: Abdominal trauma is common in children, and pancreatic injuries are either without symptoms and signs or may cause acute abdomen. **Objective:** Analysis of incidence and therapeutic treatment pseudocyst pancreas. **Methods:** The study included patients admitted in a five-year period (2005-2009). In addition to anamnestic data and examination, laboratory tests, ultrasonography and CT scan were done. Patients were admitted to the intensive therapy unit. Therapeutic treatment included the suspension of feeding, parenteral fluids and electrolytes, nasogastric decompression with active suction, antibiotics, analgesics, H₂ receptor blockers and / or proton pump, and sometimes the application of Somatostatin. Treatment is continued with either conservative or operative methods. **Results:** 7 patients (3 male and 4 female), aged 3-13 years (mean 7.7 years). Mechanism of injury: 4 - bicycle accidents, 1 - other blunt trauma, 1 - application of Anticonvulsant (Eftil). One patient had congenital anomaly (pancreas divisum). Amylase values were several times above normal values in all patients. Total perenteral nutrition (TPN) lasted in average for 26 days (3-42); 3 patients were fed through nasojejunal tube. The average stay in hospital was 61 days (14-146). Somatostatin therapy was applied in 3 patients. Two patients were treated without surgery operative external drainage was performed in 2 patients, and in 3 patients internal Roux--en - Y- cistoenterostomy was performed. Lethal outcome occurred in 1 patient. **Conclusion:** Pseudocysts of pancreas are rare in children and usually develop as the result of blunt trauma. The treatment is complex and long with questionable outcome.